

Innovation Networks of Cork, Resins and Edibles in the Mediterranean basin - INCREDIBLE

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Reference

Marini Govigli, V., Briers S., Adams, S., Martinez De Arano, I., Bonet, J.A. Andriguetto, N., Giacomoni, J., Baudriller, H., Chapelet, B., Brenko, A., Bursic, D., Calvo, J., Cristóbal, R., Hardillier, C., Maltoni, S., Mutke, S., Paulo, J.A., Santos-Silva, C., Stara, K., Markos, N., Taghouti, I., Tomé, M., Vidale, E., Redondo, C. (2021) Project publication “Knowledge in practice” - Deliverable 4.3. H2020 project no. 774632 RUR-2017-1 European Commission, 9 pp.

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List of abbreviations

The following acronyms have been used across this document:

- **AMP** Aromatic and medicinal plants
- **D** Deliverable
- **iNet** Innovation network
- **MS** Milestone
- **NWFP(s)** Non-wood forest product(s)
- **WP** Work Package

1. Executive Summary

D4.3 presents the knowledge transfer activities to targeted stakeholders that INCREDIBLE partners performed over the duration of the project. It lists articles in sectorial and practitioners' magazines and journals as well as articles targeted at broader audiences (e.g. blogs or web-stories) published at both national and international level. The dissemination items are subdivided per thematic iNets (Aromatic and medicinal plants; Cork; Mushrooms and truffles; Resins; Wild nuts and berries), and inter-iNets activities. This deliverable details how key project outcomes, process, and lessons learned from the iterative multi-actor processes have been disseminated to target audiences outside the project, as to increase the project impact and outreach.

2. Introduction

2.1. Purpose

The aim of INCREDIBLE thematic network is creating and animating a Mediterranean NWFP multiactor network, which can systematize the process of knowledge sharing, and bridge the research and innovation divide in forestry and rural development across NWFPs among actors. Along these lines, Deliverable 4.3 provides an overview of the knowledge transfer activities to targeted stakeholders that INCREDIBLE partners performed over the duration of the project. It covers both (i) articles in sectorial and practitioners’ magazines and journals as well as (ii) articles targeted at broader audiences (e.g. blogs or web-stories). The purpose of this deliverable is showcasing how key project outcomes on NWFPs across iNets, and lessons learned from the iterative multi-actor processes have been disseminated to target audiences outside the project, as to increase the project impact and outreach.

2.2. Scope

D 4.3 is articulated in the following chapters:

- Sections 1 to 4 defines the purpose and scope of the document listing Tables and Figures in use.
- Sections 5 to 9 presents the dissemination items published for each thematic iNet (Aromatic and medicinal plants; Cork; Mushrooms and truffles; Resins; Wild nuts and berries).
- Section 10 lists inter-iNets dissemination articles, while Section 11 present an overview of the articles still in preparation at the time the document was drafted.

3. Tables

3.1. Applicable documents

The following documents, of the exact issue shown, form part of this document to the extent specified herein. Applicable documents are those referenced in the Contract or approved by the Approval Authority.

Table 3-1 Applicable Documents

Ref	Title	Code	Version	Date
AD1	A Road Map for innovating NWFPs value chains - Deliverable 1.3 - reviewed	D1.3	2	2019

4. Aromatic and Medicinal Plants

4.1. “Knowledge in practice” articles on Aromatic and Medicinal Plants – An overview

The **iNet of Aromatic & Medicinal Plants** aims at monitoring the ANP value chain as to support pan-Mediterranean actors in identify priority themes for Aromatic & Medicinal Plants sustainable production and domestication, harvesting, transformation, and commercialization (AD1). This iNet focuses on wild plants with relevant market potential and that pose specific challenges related to (i) supply arrangements, (ii) value-chain scaling-up, (iii) internalization of black and informal markets.

INCREDIBLE partners performed 31 dissemination items specifically related to the topic of Aromatic and Medicinal Plants, across three countries (Greece, Spain, and Tunisia), including three dissemination items published at international level. These articles consist of 15 articles in sectorial and practitioners’ magazines and journals (e.g. forest and environmental issues sectorial environmental magazines, institutional blogs targeted to forestry practitioners, etc.) as well as 16 articles targeted at broader audiences (e.g. national, regional newspapers and non-specialists blogs and forums). The complete lists of items is provided in Section 4.2.

4.2. Table of dissemination items

Table 2. Dissemination items of the Aromatic and Medicinal Plants iNet.

Date	MEDIA/JOURNAL	COUNTRY	LEVEL	LANGUAGE	TITLE	AUDIENCE TYPE	LINK
31/01/2020	geotee.gr	Greece	National	Greek	Ειδήσεις-Νέα-> Συνέδρια Ημερίδες - Τρέχον Έτος	Sectoral / specialised public	https://www.geotee.gr/MainNewsDetail.aspx?CatID=1&RefID=23175&TabID=5
29/01/2020	amna.gr	Greece	National	Greek	"Αγρο-ταυτότητα" για τα αυθεντικά ντόπια προϊόντα μέσω DNA	Generalist media / general public	https://www.amna.gr/macedonia/article/426279/Agro-tautotita-gia-ta-authentika-ntopia-proionta-meso-DNA?fbclid=IwAR2mysMSKHzhgGqIMZZM-80pU3v8d2vt0h9eODc-NfgTNYzbxP9SN3br3U
29/01/2020	proinoslogos.gr	Greece	Regional	Greek	Προστασία φαρμακευτικών φυτών και ανίχνευση νοθεύσεων στα τρόφιμα	Generalist media / general public	https://www.proinoslogos.gr/epikairota/42-koinonia/58316-%CF%80%CF%81%CE%BF%CF%83%CF%84%CE%B1%CF%83%CE%AF%CE%B1-%CF%86%CE%B1%CF%81%CE%BC%CE%B1%CE%BA%CE%B5%CF%85%CF%84%CE%B9%CE%BA%CF%8E%CE%BD-%CF%86%CF%85%CF%84%CF%8E%CE%BD-%CE%BA%CE%B1%CE%B9-%CE%B1%CE%BD%CE%AF%CF%87%CE%BD%CE%B5%CF%85%CF%83%CE%B7-%CE%BD%CE%BF%CE%B8%CE%B5%CF%8D%CF%83%CE%B5%CF%89%CE%BD-%CF%83%CF%84%CE%B1-%CF%84%CF%81%CF%8C%CF%86%CE%B9%CE%BC%CE%B1
28/01/2020	neapaseges.gr	Greece	National	Greek	Στο επίκεντρο το παράνομο εμπόριο φαρμακευτικών φυτών	Sectoral / specialised public	https://www.neapaseges.gr/el/products/details/EIDISEIS/Sto-epikentro-to-paranomo-emporio-farmakeytikon-fyton
28/01/2020	typos-i.gr	Greece	Local	Greek	Παρακολουθώντας γονιδιακά τα φαρμακευτικά φυτά	Generalist media / general public	https://typos-i.gr/article/parakoloy8wntas-gonidiaka-ta-farmakeytika-fyta
28/01/2020	ilialive.gr	Greece	National	Greek	Στο επίκεντρο το παράνομο εμπόριο φαρμακευτικών φυτών. Εκδήλωση στο πλαίσιο του προγράμματος INCREDIBLE	Sectoral / specialised public	https://www.ilialive.gr/gaia365/%CE%B2%CE%B9%CE%BF%CE%BB%CE%BF%CE%B3%CE%B9%CE%BA%CE%AC/24649-%CF%83%CF%84%CE%BF-%CE%B5%CF%80%CE%AF%CE%BA%CE%B5%CE%BD%CF%84%CF%81%CE%BF-%CF%84%CE%BF-%CF%80%CE%B1%CF%81%CE%AC%CE%BD%CE%BF%CE%BC%CE%BF-%CE%B5%CE%BC%CF%80%CF%8C%CF%81%CE%B9%CE%BF-%CF%86%CE%B1%CF%81%CE%BC%CE%B1%CE%BA%CE%B5%CF%85%CF%84%CE%B9%CE%BA%CF%8E%CE%BD-%CF%86%CF%85%CF%84%CF%8E%CE%BD.html
15/08/2019	dimotiko radiofono	Greece	Regional	Greek	Φαρμακευτικά φυτά και εφαρμογές τους στην σύγχρονη ιατρική	Generalist media / general public	http://www.dimotikoradiofono.gr/%CE%B7%CE%BC%CE%B5%CF%81%CE%AF%CE%B4%CE%B1-%CE%BC%CE%B5-%CF%84%CE%AF%CF%84%CE%BB%CE%BF-%CF%86%CE%B1%CF%81%CE%BC%CE%B1%CE%BA%CE%B5%CF%85%CF%84%CE%B9%CE%BA%CE%AC-%CF%86%CF%85%CF%84%CE%AC-%CE%BA%CE%B1/
15/08/2019	ellinikigeorgia.gr	Greece	National	Greek	Φαρμακευτικά φυτά και εφαρμογές τους στην σύγχρονη ιατρική	Sectoral / specialised public	https://www.ellinikigeorgia.gr/ekdilosi-farmakeutika-futa-kai-efarmoges-tous-sti-sugxroni-iatriki/?fbclid=IwAR0SkRmp8mbyvUGoAmCy8_I0qCFQikKoEDv6KDVZPqHq5irk7pV-7jNXGMA
15/08/2019	Duth	Greece	National	Greek	Φαρμακευτικά φυτά και εφαρμογές τους στην σύγχρονη ιατρική	Sectoral / specialised public	http://career.duth.gr/portal/?q=node/77866#.XN_GmsgzaUk

15/08/2019	epirusin	Greece	Regional	Greek	Φαρμακευτικά φυτά και εφαρμογές τους στην σύγχρονη ιατρική	Generalist media / general public	http://epirusin.blogspot.com/2019/05/blog-post_9.html
15/08/2019	Agro24	Greece	National	Greek	Φαρμακευτικά φυτά και εφαρμογές τους στην σύγχρονη ιατρική	Sectoral / specialised public	https://www.agro24.gr/agrotika/agrotiki-epikairota/farmakeytika-fyta-kai-efarmoges-toys-stin-syghroni-iatriki
15/08/2019	Texnologos geponos	Greece	National	Greek	Φαρμακευτικά φυτά και εφαρμογές τους στην σύγχρονη ιατρική	Sectoral / specialised public	http://www.texnologosgeponos.gr/2019/05/blog-post_7.html
15/08/2019	geotee.gr	Greece	Regional	Greek	Φαρμακευτικά φυτά και εφαρμογές τους στην σύγχρονη ιατρική	Sectoral / specialised public	https://www.geotee.gr/MainNewsDetail.aspx?CatID=1&RefID=22527&TabID=4
15/08/2019	proinoslogos.gr	Greece	Regional	Greek	Φαρμακευτικά φυτά και εφαρμογές τους στην σύγχρονη ιατρική	Generalist media / general public	https://proinoslogos.gr/epikairota/42-koinonia/53653-%CF%86%CE%B1%CF%81%CE%BC%CE%B1%CE%BA%CE%B5%CF%85%CF%84%CE%B9%CE%BA%CE%AC-%CF%86%CF%85%CF%84%CE%AC-%CE%BA%CE%B1%CE%B9-%CF%83%CF%8D%CE%B3%CF%87%CF%81%CE%BF%CE%BD%CE%B7-%CE%B9%CE%B1%CF%84%CF%81%CE%B9%CE%BA%CE%AE-%CE%B8%CE%AD%CE%BC%CE%B1-%CE%B7%CE%BC%CE%B5%CF%81%CE%AF%CE%B4%CE%B1%CF%82
15/08/2019	Epirusmeteo	Greece	Regional	Greek	Φαρμακευτικά φυτά και εφαρμογές τους στην σύγχρονη ιατρική	Generalist media / general public	https://www.epirusmeteo.gr/2019/05/blog-post_6.html
15/08/2019	epirus online	Greece	Regional	Greek	Φαρμακευτικά φυτά και εφαρμογές τους στην σύγχρονη ιατρική	Generalist media / general public	https://www.epirusonline.gr/index.php/listing-2-columns-news-22/item/14214-imerida-me-titlo-farmakeftika-fyta-kai-efarmoges-tous-stin-syghroni-iatriki
04/06/2019	dasarxeio.com	Greece	National	Greek	Μη Ξυλώδη Δασικά προϊόντα και εμπόριο, δύο διαπεριφερειακά σεμινάρια	Sectoral / specialised public	https://dasarxeio.com/2019/06/04/67977/
04/06/2019	Municipality radio of Ioannina	Greece	Local	Greek	Μη Ξυλώδη Δασικά προϊόντα και εμπόριο, δύο διαπεριφερειακά σεμινάρια	Generalist media / general public	http://www.dimotikoradiofono.gr/%CE%BC%CE%B7-%CE%BE%CF%85%CE%BB%CF%8E%CE%B4%CE%B7-%CE%B4%CE%B1%CF%83%CE%B9%CE%BA%CE%AC-%CF%80%CF%81%CE%BF%CF%8A%CF%8C%CE%BD%CF%84%CE%B1-%CE%BA%CE%B1%CE%B9-%CE%B5%CE%BC%CF%80%CF%8C%CF%81%CE%B9%CE%BF/
04/06/2019	Municipality of Zagori	Greece	Local	Greek	Μη Ξυλώδη Δασικά προϊόντα και εμπόριο, δύο διαπεριφερειακά σεμινάρια	Generalist media / general public	https://www.zagori.gov.gr/?p=19583
04/06/2019	typos-i	Greece	Local	Greek	Μη Ξυλώδη Δασικά προϊόντα και εμπόριο, δύο διαπεριφερειακά σεμινάρια	Generalist media / general public	https://typos-i.gr/article/dyo-seminaria-gia-arwmatika-fyta-kai-manitaria
07/05/2019	ert.gr	Greece	Regional	Greek	Φαρμακευτικά φυτά και εφαρμογές τους στην σύγχρονη ιατρική	Generalist media / general public	https://www.ert.gr/perifereiakoi-stathmoi/ioanina/imerida-gia-ta-farmakeytika-fyta/
06/05/2019	epirus-tv-news.gr	Greece	Regional	Greek	Ιωάννινα :Ενημερωτική Εκδήλωση Με Θέμα "Φαρμακευτικά Φυτά Και	Generalist media / general public	http://www.epirus-tv-news.gr/2019/05/blog-post_893.html

					Εφαρμογές Τους Στην Σύγχρονη Ιατρική"		
06/05/2019	news.makedonias.gr	Greece	Regional	Greek	Φαρμακευτικά φυτά και εφαρμογές τους στην σύγχρονη ιατρική	Generalist media / general public	https://news.makedonias.gr/2019/05/117798/
06/05/2019	dasarxeio.com	Greece	National	Greek	Εκδήλωση: Φαρμακευτικά Φυτά και Εφαρμογές τους στην Σύγχρονη Ιατρική	Sectoral / specialised public	https://dasarxeio.com/2019/05/06/67281/
06/05/2019	typos-i.gr	Greece	Local	Greek	Ημερίδα για τα φαρμακευτικά φυτά	Generalist media / general public	https://typos-i.gr/article/hmerida-gia-ta-farmakeytika-fyta
06/05/2019	epiruspost.gr	Greece	Regional	Greek	Φαρμακευτικά φυτά και εφαρμογές τους στην σύγχρονη ιατρική	Generalist media / general public	https://www.epiruspost.gr/diafora/ekdiloseis/67331-imerida-gia-ta-farmakeytika-fyta
07/2020	EIP-AGRI report	Interregional	International	English	EIP-AGRI Focus Group Plant-based medicinal and cosmetic products	Sectoral / specialised public	https://ec.europa.eu/eip/agriculture/en/publications/eip-agri-focus-group-plant-based-medicinal-and
06/05/2019	MedForest	Interregional	International	English	Medicinal plants and their uses in modern Medicine	Sectoral / specialised public	https://medforest.net/2019/05/06/medicinal-plants-and-their-uses-in-modern-medicine/
30/07/2018	MedForest	Interregional	International	English	International Congress on medicinal plants and bio-agriculture	Sectoral / specialised public	https://medforest.net/2018/07/30/international-congress-on-medicinal-plants-and-bio-agriculture/
29/07/2019	CTFC Blog	Spain	National	Spanish	Visita a experiencias productivas de plantas aromáticas y medicinales	Sectoral / specialised public	http://blog.ctfc.cat/es/visita-a-experiencias-productivas-de-plantas-aromaticas-y-medicinales/
20/06/2018	Institution de la Recherche et de l'Enseignement Supérieur Agricoles (IRESA)	Tunisia	International	English	INRGREF will host an international seminar to promote the sector of Aromatic and Medicinal Plants	Sectoral / specialised public	http://www.iresa.agrinet.tn/pdfs/INRGREF%20AMP%20scoping%20seminar.pdf

5. Cork

5.1. “Knowledge in practice” articles on Cork – An overview

The **iNet of Cork** aims at identifying which factors mostly influence the cork value chain, and improve it across the Mediterranean through innovation development, knowledge transfer, and enhanced profitability to sustain management (AD1). It focuses on sharing innovative solutions for the Cork market covering (i): improved profitability of cork production, (ii) optimization of supply arrangements, and (iii) development of new business models for enhanced market penetration.

Seven dissemination items have been produced specifically related to the iNet of Cork, including four national items produced at Portuguese and Italian level, one at French level, and two dissemination items published at international level. The complete lists of items is provided in Section 5.2.

5.2. Table of dissemination items

Table 3. Dissemination items of the Cork iNet

Date	MEDIA/JOURNAL	COUNTRY	LEVEL	LANGUAGE	TITLE	AUDIENCE TYPE	LINK
11/2020	CICYTEX website	Spain	National	Spanish	TRAINING SESSION ONLINE- Cork quality assessment. 18 y 19 de noviembre	Sectoral / specialised public	http://cicytex.juntaex.es/es/eventos/649/training-session-online-cork-quality-assessment-18-y-19-de-noviembre
8- 9/11/2020	IV Rural Innovation Forum	Spain / Portugal	National	Spanish / Portugese	Conceição Santos presents INCREDIBLE Project at PANEL 4 Aprovechamiento del bosque	Sectoral / specialised public	https://www.facebook.com/ruralinnoforum/
04/09/2019	agroportal.pt	Portugal	National	Portuguese	Observatório do Sobreiro e da Cortiça recebe encontro sobre pesquisa nos sistemas agroflorestais	Sectoral / specialised public	https://www.agroportal.pt/observatorio-do-sobreiro-e-da-cortica-recebe-encontro-sobre-pesquisa-nos-sistemas-agroflorestais/
14/06/2019	sardegnaforeste.it	Italy	Regional	Italian	La qualità del sughero, i mercati emergenti del Mediterraneo	Sectoral / specialised public	http://www.sardegnaforeste.it/notizia/la-qualita%C3%A0-del-sughero-i-mercati-emergenti-del-mediterraneo
20/04/2019	MedForest	Interregional	International	English	Cork market and cork quality assessment in the Mediterranean	Sectoral / specialised public	https://medforest.net/2019/04/20/cork-quality-and-cork-quality-assessment-in-the-mediterranean/
29/03/2019	Corse Matin	France	National	French	Le liège en quête de noblesse	Generalist media / general public	https://www.corsematin.com/articles/le-liege-corse-en-quete-de-noblesse-91778
28/09/2018	MedForest	Interregional	International	English	“Wood first” takes a back seat in Sardinia	Sectoral / specialised public	https://medforest.net/2018/09/28/wood-first-takes-a-back-seat-in-sardinia/

6. Mushrooms and Truffles

6.1. “Knowledge in practice” articles on Mushrooms and Truffles – An overview

The **iNet of Mushrooms and Truffles** aims at bringing together actors from the recreational level (e.g. occasional pickers), the commercial level (e.g. mushroom traders), as well as activities proper of the tertiary sector, as to foster knowledge-sharing around new production models and value chain reorganization which can enhance the economic performance of the sector and share benefit across all involved shareholders. (AD1).

INCREDIBLE partners performed 48 dissemination items on Mushrooms and Truffles- sectorial topics, across two main countries: Greece and Spain. These articles include 22 articles in sectorial and practitioners’ magazines and journals (e.g., institutional webs, environmental magazines, blogs targeted to forestry practitioners, etc.) as well as 26 articles targeted at broader audiences (e.g. national, regional newspapers and non-specialists blogs and forums). The complete list of items is provided in Section 6.2.

6.2. Table of dissemination items

Table 4. Dissemination items of the Mushrooms and Truffles iNet

Date	MEDIA/JOURNAL	COUNTRY	LEVEL	LANGUAGE	TITLE	AUDIENCE TYPE	LINK
15/02/2020	Department of BAT, UOI news	Greece	National	Greek	Μανιτάρια και τρούφες: Από το δάσος στο τραπέζι	Sectoral / specialised public	https://www.uoi.gr/events/manitaria-kai-troyfes-apo-to-dasos-sto-trapezi/
15/02/2020	typos-i	Greece	Local	Greek	Μανιτάρια και τρούφες: Από το δάσος στο τραπέζι	Generalist media / general public	https://typos-i.gr/article/manitaria-apo-dasos-sto-trapezi
15/02/2020	Epirus TV	Greece	Regional	Greek	Ιωάννινα:Εκδήλωση Αύριο Με Θέμα "Μανιτάρια Και Τρούφες: Από Το Δάσος Στο Τραπέζι"	Generalist media / general public	http://www.epirus-tv-news.gr/2020/02/blog-post_250.html
09/06/2019	typos-i	Greece	Local	Greek	Μανιτάρια: Από το δάσος στην αγορά	Generalist media / general public	https://typos-i.gr/article/manitaria-apo-dasos-sthn-agma?fbclid=IwAR2TfIU5I22WNHylepT806tkeYxDxni_iUqrAjUORa_XPYnBrUYgASjpB_4
04/06/2019	Department of BAT, UOI news	Greece	National	Greek	Μη Ξυλώδη Δασικά προϊόντα και εμπόριο, δύο διαπεριφερειακά σεμινάρια	Sectoral / specialised public	http://www.bat.uoi.gr/show-news/itemlist/user/87-%CE%BA%CE%B1%CE%BB%CE%BB%CE%B9%CF%8C%CF%80%CE%B7%CF%83%CF%84%CE%AC%CF%81%CE%B1
04/06/2019	University of Ioannina website	Greece	National	Greek	Μη Ξυλώδη Δασικά προϊόντα και εμπόριο, δύο διαπεριφερειακά σεμινάρια	Sectoral / specialised public	https://www.uoi.gr/events/manitaria-kai-troyfes-tropoi-veltiosis-tis-poiotitas-kai-katastasis-tis-agogas/
04/06/2019	dasarxeio.com	Greece	National	Greek	Μη Ξυλώδη Δασικά προϊόντα και εμπόριο, δύο διαπεριφερειακά σεμινάρια	Sectoral / specialised public	https://dasarxeio.com/2019/06/04/67977/
04/06/2019	Municipality radio of Ioannina	Greece	Local	Greek	Μη Ξυλώδη Δασικά προϊόντα και εμπόριο, δύο διαπεριφερειακά σεμινάρια	Generalist media / general public	http://www.dimotikoradiofono.gr/%CE%BC%CE%B7-%CE%BE%CF%85%CE%BB%CF%8E%CE%B4%CE%B7-%CE%B4%CE%B1%CF%83%CE%B9%CE%BA%CE%AC-%CF%80%CF%81%CE%BF%CF%8A%CF%8C%CE%BD%CF%84%CE%B1-%CE%BA%CE%B1%CE%B9-%CE%B5%CE%BC%CF%80%CF%8C%CF%81%CE%B9%CE%BF/
04/06/2019	Municipality of Zagori	Greece	Local	Greek	Μη Ξυλώδη Δασικά προϊόντα και εμπόριο, δύο διαπεριφερειακά σεμινάρια	Generalist media / general public	https://www.zagori.gov.gr/?p=19583
04/06/2019	typos-i	Greece	Local	Greek	Μη Ξυλώδη Δασικά προϊόντα και εμπόριο, δύο διαπεριφερειακά σεμινάρια	Generalist media / general public	https://typos-i.gr/article/dyo-seminaria-gia-arwmatika-fyta-kai-manitaria
20/05/2019 ¹	healthyliving	Greece	National	Greek	Τα «θαυματουργά» βοτάνια από τους «κομπογιαννίτες» έως τους σύγχρονους επιστήμονες	Sectoral / specialised public	https://www.healthyliving.gr/2019/05/20/vikogiatroi-kompogiannites-9/

19/05/2019 ⁴	Geo news	Greece	National	Greek	Τα «θαυματουργά» βοτάνια από τους «κομπογιαννίτες» έως τους σύγχρονους επιστήμονες	Sectoral / specialised public	https://geonews.gr/%CE%B1%CF%80%CF%8C-%CF%84%CE%BF%CF%85%CF%82-%CE%B2%CE%B9%CE%BA%CE%BF%CE%B3%CE%B9%CE%B1%CF%84%CF%81%CE%BF%CF%8D%CF%82-%CE%BA%CE%B1%CE%B9-%CF%84%CE%BF%CF%85%CF%82-%CE%BA%CE%BF%CE%BC/
19/05/2019 ⁴	zougla.gr	Greece	National	Greek	Τα «θαυματουργά» βοτάνια από τους «κομπογιαννίτες» έως τους σύγχρονους επιστήμονες	Generalist media / general public	https://www.zougla.gr/ygeia/article/apo-tous-vikogiatrous-ke-tous-kompogianites-stous-sigxronous-episthmones
19/05/2019 ⁴	kathimerini (interview)	Greece	National	Greek	Τα «θαυματουργά» βοτάνια από τους «κομπογιαννίτες» έως τους σύγχρονους επιστήμονες	Generalist media / general public	http://www.kathimerini.gr/1024763/article/epikairothta/ellada/ta-8avmatovrga-votania-apo-toys-kompogiannites-ews-toys-syvxronoys-episthmones
15/05/2019	Municipality of Zagori	Greece	Local	Greek	«Τρούφες: Αποκαλύπτοντας τους θησαυρούς του δάσους», ημερίδα σήμερα στο Πανεπιστήμιο Ιωαννίνων	Generalist media / general public	http://www.zagori.gov.gr/?p=19494
15/05/2019	epirus tv news	Greece	Regional	Greek	«Τρούφες: Αποκαλύπτοντας τους θησαυρούς του δάσους», ημερίδα σήμερα στο Πανεπιστήμιο Ιωαννίνων	Generalist media / general public	http://www.epirus-tv-news.gr/2019/05/blog-post_985.html
15/05/2019	dasarxeio.com	Greece	National	Greek	«Τρούφες: Αποκαλύπτοντας τους θησαυρούς του δάσους», ημερίδα σήμερα στο Πανεπιστήμιο Ιωαννίνων	Sectoral / specialised public	https://dasarxeio.com/2019/05/13/67566/
15/05/2019	troufaclub fb	Greece	National	Greek	«Τρούφες: Αποκαλύπτοντας τους θησαυρούς του δάσους», ημερίδα σήμερα στο Πανεπιστήμιο Ιωαννίνων	Sectoral / specialised public	https://www.facebook.com/troufaclub/
15/05/2019	uoi web page	Greece	National	Greek	«Τρούφες: Αποκαλύπτοντας τους θησαυρούς του δάσους», ημερίδα σήμερα στο Πανεπιστήμιο Ιωαννίνων	Sectoral / specialised public	https://www.uoi.gr/events/troyfes-apokalyptontas-toys-thisayroys-toy-dasoys/
15/05/2019	Department of BAT, UOI news	Greece	National	Greek	«Τρούφες: Αποκαλύπτοντας τους θησαυρούς του δάσους», ημερίδα σήμερα στο Πανεπιστήμιο Ιωαννίνων	Sectoral / specialised public	http://www.bat.uoi.gr/show-news/item/4162-https-www-incredibleforest-net-content-truffles-revealing-treasures-forest
07/06/2019	Diputación de Zamora Press Service	Spain	Local	Spanish	La Diputación de Zamora expone en un simposio en Grecia su experiencia sobre la regulación micológica en la provincia	Generalist media / general public	http://www.diputaciondezamora.es/index.asp?MP=8&MS=22&MN=2&TR=A&IDR=18&i d=2202&r=1920*1080
07/06/2019	Agencia ICAL	Spain	Regional	Spanish	La Diputación de Zamora explica en un simposio en Grecia su experiencia en cuanto a la regulación micológica	Generalist media / general public	not available.

07/06/2019	zamoranews.com	Spain	Local	Spanish	La regulación micológica en Zamora ponencia en un simposio en Grecia	Generalist media / general public	https://zamoranews.com/enogastronomia/item/45248-la-regulacion-micologica-en-zamora-ponencia-en-un-simposio-en-grecia
07/06/2019	zamora24horas.com	Spain	Local	Spanish	La experiencia sobre la regulación micológica en la provincia llega a Grecia a través de la Diputación	Generalist media / general public	https://www.zamora24horas.com/texto-diario/mostrar/1446730/experiencia-sobre-regulacion-micologica-provincia-llega-grecia-traves-diputacion
18/12/2018	Newsletter <i>Indforma</i>	Spain	National	Spanish	Expertos sugieren el establecimiento de una normativa para setas y trufas del Mediterráneo	Sectoral / specialised public	http://ceseфор.com/noticias/expertos-sugieren-el-establecimiento-de-una-normativa-para-setas-y-trufas-del-mediterraneo
14/11/2018	CTFC web	Spain	Regional	Catalan	Vedats de bolets, oportunitats de rendibilitat forestal i la seva legalitat, a debat el 19 de novembre	Sectoral / specialised public	http://blog.ctfc.cat/ca/vedats-de-bolets-oportunitats-de-rendibilitat-forestal-i-la-seva-legalitat-a-debat-el-19-de-novembre/
09/11/2018	Newsletter <i>Indforma</i>	Spain	National	Spanish	Jornada del proyecto INCREDBLE sobre el marco de regulación micológica y las oportunidades de su aplicación	Sectoral / specialised public	http://www.ceseфор.com/noticias/jornada-del-proyecto-incredibile-sobre-el-marco-de-regulacion-micologica-y-las-oportunidades
26/06/2018	diariodeteruel.es	Spain	Local	Spanish	Jean Charles Savignac, presidente del GETT: “Falta trufa en el mundo, es un producto deficitario desde siempre”	Generalist media / general public	https://diariodeteruel.es/noticia.asp?notid=1006902&secid=8
22/06/2018	Newsletter <i>Indforma</i>	Spain	National	Spanish	Representantes de la cadena de valor de las setas y trufas en el Mediterráneo celebran un encuentro internacional en España	Sectoral / specialised public	http://www.ceseфор.com/noticias/representantes-de-la-cadena-de-valor-de-las-setas-y-trufas-en-el-mediterraneo-celebran-un
22/06/2018	diariodeteruel.es	Spain	Local	Spanish	La trufa negra es la reina de un mercado que plantea abrirse a otras variedades	Generalist media / general public	http://www.diariodeteruel.es/noticialmpimir.asp?notid=1006786
20/06/2018	Aragón TV	Spain	Regional	Spanish	El encuentro en Sarrión del proyecto INCREDBLE en Aragón TV	Generalist media / general public	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=WcU8z1dKnIw
19/06/2018	RTVCyL	Spain	Regional	Spanish	Seminario INCREDBLE. A partir del 8'	Generalist media / general public	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=B3oXc6mhL2I
19/06/2018	pinarenoticias.com	Spain	Local	Spanish	La revalorización de las setas y trufas busca un análisis común en el área del Mediterráneo	Generalist media / general public	http://www.pinarenoticias.com/articulo/forestal/revalorizacion-setas-trufas-centra-seminario-expertos-mediterraneo-busca/20180619131925014357.html
19/06/2018	CITA Aragón website	Spain	Regional	Spanish	Sarrión acoge un encuentro internacional mediterráneo que debatirá sobre el futuro del mundo de la trufa	Sectoral / specialised public	https://www.cita-aragon.es/es/noticias/sarrión-acoge-un-encuentro-internacional-mediterraneo-que-debatira-sobre-el-futuro-del

18/06/2018	Aragón Hoy	Spain	Regional	Spanish	Sarrión acoge un encuentro internacional mediterráneo que debatirá sobre el futuro del mundo de la trufa	Generalist media / general public	http://www.aragonhoy.net/index.php/mod.noticias/mem.detalle/area.1055/id.224342
17/06/2018	El Mundo. Herald-Diario de Soria	Spain	Local	Spanish	Encuentro internacional de setas y trufas	Generalist media / general public	not available.
17/06/2018	pinarenoticias.com	Spain	Local	Spanish	El Cesefor acoge un seminario internacional sobre la cadena de valor de las setas en el Mediterráneo	Generalist media / general public	http://www.pinarenoticias.com/articulo/forestal/el-cesefor/20180617105306014333.html
16/06/2018	elmirondesoria.es	Spain	Local	Spanish	Encuentro internacional en Soria de la cadena de valor de setas y trufas	Generalist media / general public	https://elmirondesoria.es/soria/capital/encuentro-internacional-en-soria-de-la-cadena-de-valor-de-setas-y-trufas
16/06/2018	sorianoticias.com	Spain	Local	Spanish	Encuentro internacional en Soria y Teruel de representantes de la cadena de valor de las setas y trufas en el Mediterráneo	Generalist media / general public	http://sorianoticias.com/noticia/2018-06-16-encuentro-internacional-soria-terue-representantes-cadena-valor-setas-trufas-mediterraneo-49433
16/06/2018	desdesoria.es	Spain	Local	Spanish	Representantes de la cadena de valor de las setas y trufas celebran un encuentro internacional en Soria y Teruel	Generalist media / general public	http://www.desdesoria.es/2018/06/16/representantes-de-la-cadena-de-valor-de-las-setas-y-trufas-celebran-un-encuentro-internacional-en-soria-y-teruel/
16/06/2018	agronewscastillayleon.com	Spain	Local	Spanish	Representantes de la cadena de valor de las setas y trufas en el Mediterráneo celebran la semana próxima un encuentro internacional en Soria y Teruel	Sectoral / specialised public	http://www.agronewscastillayleon.com/representantes-de-la-cadena-de-valor-de-las-setas-y-trufas-en-el-mediterraneo-celebran-la-semana
07/05/2018	El Mundo. Herald-Diario de Soria	Spain	Local	Spanish	El seminario del EMI sobre hongos y trufas del proyecto INCREDIBLE será a finales de junio	Generalist media / general public	not available.
10/07/2019	MedForest	Interregional	International	English	Greece releases legislation proposal on wild edible mushrooms	Sectoral / specialised public	https://medforest.net/2019/07/10/greece-releases-legislation-proposal-on-wild-edible-mushrooms/
17/04/2019	MedForest	Interregional	International	English	Mushrooms and truffles: ways of improving quality and markets status	Sectoral / specialised public	https://medforest.net/2019/04/17/mushrooms-and-truffles-ways-of-improving-quality-and-markets-status/
17/12/2018	EFIMED Network News	Interregional	International	English	Regulation required for Mediterranean mushrooms and truffles	Sectoral / specialised public	https://efi.int/articles/regulation-required-mediterranean-mushrooms-and-truffles
21/11/2018	MedForest	Interregional	International	English	Science to practice focus on regulated areas for mushroom picking	Sectoral / specialised public	https://medforest.net/2018/11/21/science-to-practice-focus-on-regulated-areas-for-mushroom-picking/
09/11/2018	MedForest	Interregional	International	English	Mushroom regulation: An opportunity for adding value to our forests	Sectoral / specialised public	https://medforest.net/2018/11/09/mushroom-regulation-an-opportunity-for-adding-value-to-our-forests/

28/06/2018	EFIMED Network News	Interregional	International	English	Wild Mushrooms & Truffles seminar shapes the direction of a new innovation network for the sector	Sectoral / specialised public	not available.
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¹Dissemination items referring also to the Aromatic and Medicinal Plants iNet.

7. Resins

7.1. “Knowledge in practice” articles on Resins – An overview

The **iNet of Resins** aims at exploring the existing best practices across European gum resin value chain. Its main objectives are: (i) to improve the natural resin production system of Mediterranean forests to supply the local industry; (ii) to generate stable and quality employment in the rural areas of the Mediterranean region through resin extraction activities; (iii) to valorize and promote the natural resin produced in Mediterranean forests as a socially, economically and environmentally sustainable resources (AD1).

45 dissemination items were done in relation to Resins, mainly at Spanish and international level. These articles include 31 articles in sectorial and practitioners’ magazines and journals (as well as 16 articles targeted at broader audiences (e.g. national, regional newspapers and non-specialists blogs and forums). The complete lists of items is provided in Section 7.2.

7.2. Table of dissemination items

Table 5. Dissemination items of the Resins iNet

Date	MEDIA/JOURNAL	COUNTRY	LEVEL	LANGUAGE	TITLE	AUDIENCE TYPE	LINK
24/01/2019	labrit-roquefort.blogs.sudouest.fr	France	Regional	French	"Gemme la forêt d'Aquitaine" s'installe sur la commune	Sectoral / specialised public	http://labrit-roquefort.blogs.sudouest.fr/archive/2019/01/24/gemme-la-foret-d-aquitaine-s-installe-sur-la-commune-1069029.html
11/12/2020	Newsletter Indforma	Spain	National	Spanish	El proyecto INCREDIBLE celebra la jornada de transferencia 'Redes colaborativas sobre la resina como materia prima para la bioeconomía'	Sectoral / specialised public	http://cesefor.com/noticias/el-proyecto-incredibile-celebra-la-jornada-de-transferencia-redes-colaborativas-sobre-la
06/11/2020	Newsletter Indforma	Spain	National	Spanish	Cinco ideas de innovación resinera de futuro como resultado de idiForest	Sectoral / specialised public	http://cesefor.com/noticias/cinco-ideas-de-innovacion-resinera-de-futuro-como-resultado-de-idiforest
11/2020	Distritoforestal.es	Spain	National	Spanish	Cinco ideas de innovación resinera de futuro como resultado de idiForest	Sectoral / specialised public	https://distritoforestal.es/actualidad/politica-forestal/cinco-ideas-de-innovacion-resinera-de-futuro-como-resultado-de-idiforest
27/01/2020	madera-sostenible.com	Spain	National	Spanish	Tormenta de ideas para la innovación del sector resinero	Sectoral / specialised public	https://madera-sostenible.com/panorama/tormenta-de-ideas-para-la-innovacion-del-sector-resinero/?utm_source=mailpoet&utm_medium=email&utm_campaign=boletin-madera-sostenible-27-de-diciembre-de-2019_8
20/01/2020	madera-sostenible.com	Spain	National	Spanish	Tormenta de ideas para la innovación del sector resinero	Sectoral / specialised public	https://madera-sostenible.com/forestal/tormenta-de-ideas-para-la-innovacion-del-sector-resinero/
16/01/2020	desdesoria.es	Spain	Regional	Spanish	Cesefor convoca una iniciativa de tormenta de ideas para la innovación resinera	Generalist media / general public	https://www.desdesoria.es/2020/01/16/cesefor-convoca-una-iniciativa-de-tormenta-de-ideas-para-la-innovacion-resinera/
16/01/2020	Newsletter Indforma	Spain	National	Spanish	SustForest Plus abre un proceso participativo para recoger ideas que mejoren el oficio resinero	Sectoral / specialised public	https://bit.ly/3psOTiy
16/01/2020	elmirondesoria.es	Spain	Regional	Spanish	Cesefor impulsa una "tormenta" de ideas para la innovación resinera	Generalist media / general public	https://elmirondesoria.es/cyl/castilla-y-leon/cesefor-impulsa-una-tormenta-de-ideas-para-la-innovacion-resinera
16/01/2020	sorianoticias.com	Spain	Regional	Spanish	El sector resinero busca reinventarse con una tormenta de ideas	Generalist media / general public	https://sorianoticias.com/noticia/2020-01-16-el-sector-resinero-busca-reinventarse-una-tormenta-ideas-64389
16/01/2020	agroinformacion.com	Spain	National	Spanish	El proyecto SustForest Plus lanza un reto para una nueva tormenta de ideas para la innovación resinera	Sectoral / specialised public	https://agroinformacion.com/proyecto-sustforest-plus-lanza-un-reto-para-una-nueva-tormenta-de-ideas-para-la-innovacion-resinera/

16/01/2020	Agencia ICAL	Spain	Regional	Spanish	Cesefor convoca una iniciativa de tormenta de ideas para la innovación resinera	Generalist media / general public	http://www.icalnews.com/Mostrar.cfm/noticias/l/cese-for/convoca/iniciativa/tormenta/ideas/innovacion/resinera/478256
05/01/2020	El Mundo - Diario de Valladolid	Spain	Local	Spanish	Evento internacional del H2020 INCREDIBLE sobre la modelización de recursos de la resina	Generalist media / general public	Not available.
15/11/2019	Newsletter Indforma	Spain	National	Spanish	Uso de las resinas naturales, desarrollo territorial y desafío demográfico: tu contribución es importante	Sectoral / specialised public	https://bit.ly/36iZhmR
07/11/2019	Newsletter Indforma	Spain	National	Spanish	Apoyo al sector de la resina natural como herramienta estratégica en la lucha contra la despoblación	Sectoral / specialised public	https://bit.ly/3poAp4n
30/10/2019	elmirondesori.com	Spain	Local	Spanish	Cesefor: Aprovechamiento resinero y desarrollo rural	Generalist media / general public	https://elmirondesoria.es/soria/capital/cese-for-aprovechamiento-resinero-y-desarrollo-rural
30/10/2019	Newsletter Indforma	Spain	National	Spanish	Jornada sobre el aprovechamiento resinero y su relación con el desarrollo rural para afrontar el reto demográfico	Sectoral / specialised public	https://bit.ly/3ppo2Fc
18/10/2019	UPM University website blog	Spain	National	Spanish	Jornada de innovación forestal “Science to Practice: Avances en mecanización del aprovechamiento resinero”	Sectoral / specialised public	https://blogs.upm.es/forest/2018/10/18/jornada-de-innovacion-forestal-science-to-practice-avances-en-mecanizacion-del-aprovechamiento-resinero/
08/08/2019	argentinaforestal.com	Spain	International	Spanish	España: Realizarán una expedición técnica y comercial al sector resinero de Brasil, nuevo líder internacional en producción de resina natural de pino	Sectoral / specialised public	http://www.argentinaforestal.com/2019/08/08/espana-realizaran-una-expedicion-tecnica-y-comercial-al-sector-resinero-de-brasil-nuevo-lider-internacional-en-produccion-de-resina-natural-de-pino/
22/04/2019	Sud-Ouest	France	National	French	Un nouveau souffle pour la résine de pin	Generalist media / general public	http://xylofutur.fr/wp-content/uploads/2019/04/SO-Nouveau-souffle-resine-220419.pdf
21/01/2019	agronewscastillayleon.com	Spain	Regional	Spanish	Madrid acoge hoy y mañana el workshop Monitoreo y modelización de recursos de resina en un contexto de cambio climático	Sectoral / specialised public	https://www.agronewscastillayleon.com/madrid-acoge-hoy-y-manana-el-workshop-monitoreo-y-modelizacion-de-recursos-de-resina-en-un-contexto
18/01/2019	RNE Soria	Spain	Local	Spanish	Entrevista a Javier Calvo previa a la celebración del evento INCREDIBLE en INIA	Generalist media / general public	Not available.

18/01/2019	Newsletter <i>Indforma</i>	Spain	National	Spanish	SustForest Plus presenta en el INIA su aplicación multiplataforma de trazabilidad de resinas naturales	Sectoral / specialised public	http://ceseфор.com/noticias/sustforest-plus-presenta-en-el-inia-su-aplicacion-multiplataforma-de-trazabilidad-de
17/01/2019	Boletín Electrónico del COIM nº 73	Spain	National	Spanish	Seminario internacional: Monitoreo y modelización de recursos de resina en un contexto de cambio climático	Sectoral / specialised public	https://www.ingenierosdemontes.org/boletines/20190117.html
15/01/2019	Agencia ICAL	Spain	Regional	Spanish	Madrid acoge la semana próxima un taller de trabajo internacional sobre monitoreo y modelización de recursos de resina	Generalist media / general public	http://www.icalnews.com/Mostrar.cfm/noticias/l/madrid/acoge/semana/proxima/taller/trabajo/internacional/monitoreo/modelizacion/recursos/resina/445318
15/01/2019	elmirondesoria.es	Spain	Local	Spanish	Workshop Monitoreo y modelización de recursos de resina	Generalist media / general public	https://elmirondesoria.es/provincia/noticias/workshop-monitoreo-y-modelizacion-de-recursos-de-resina
15/01/2019	sorianoticias.es	Spain	Local	Spanish	El INIA acoge la próxima semana unas jornadas sobre los recursos de la resina y el cambio climático	Generalist media / general public	http://sorianoticias.com/noticia/2019-01-15-el-inia-acoge-proxima-semana-unas-jornadas-sobre-recursos-resina-cambio-climatico-54837
15/01/2019	agroinformacion.com	Spain	National	Spanish	Workshop Monitoreo y modelización de recursos de resina en un contexto de cambio climático	Sectoral / specialised public	http://www.agroinformacion.com/workshop-monitoreo-y-modelizacion-de-recursos-de-resina-en-un-contexto-de-cambio-climatico/
15/01/2019	noticiasforestales.com	Spain	National	Spanish	Monitoreo y modelización de recursos de resina en un contexto de cambio climático	Sectoral / specialised public	http://www.noticiasforestales.com/2019/01/monitoreo-y-modelizacion-de-recursos-de.html
15/01/2019	madera-sostenible.com	Spain	National	Spanish	Madrid acoge el workshop "Monitoreo y modelización de recursos de resina en un contexto de cambio climático"	Sectoral / specialised public	https://madera-sostenible.com/forestal/madrid-acoge-el-workshop-monitoreo-y-modelizacion-de-recursos-de-resina-en-un-contexto-de-cambio-climatico/
11/01/2019	Newsletter <i>Indforma</i>	Spain	National	Spanish	Evento internacional del H2020 INCREDIBLE sobre la modelización de recursos de la resina	Sectoral / specialised public	http://www.ceseфор.com/noticias/evento-internacional-del-h2020-incredible-sobre-la-modelizacion-de-recursos-de-la-resina
23/11/2018	Portal de la Resina de Castilla y León	Spain	Regional	Spanish	La innovación y la transferencia de conocimiento, claves para impulsar el sector resinero	Sectoral / specialised public	Not available.
24/10/2018	El Mundo. Heraldo-Diario de Soria	Spain	Local	Spanish	Los resineros conocen los avances para mecanizar su trabajo	Generalist media / general public	Not available.
20/10/2018	El Mundo. Heraldo-Diario de Soria	Spain	Local	Spanish	Jornada sobre innovación en el sector resinero	Generalist media / general public	https://www.resinacyl.es/noticias/la-innovacion-la-transferencia-conocimiento-claves-impulsar-el-sector-resinero

19/10/2018	elmirondesoria.com	Spain	Local	Spanish	Tardelcuende analiza los retos de la innovación en mecanización de resinación	Generalist media / general public	https://elmirondesoria.es/provincia/comarca-de-almazan/tardelcuende-analiza-los-retos-de-la-innovacion-en-mecanizacion-de-resinacion
19/10/2018	desdesoria.es	Spain	Local	Spanish	Tardelcuende acogerá una jornada sobre innovación con la resina	Generalist media / general public	http://www.desdesoria.es/2018/10/19/tardelcuende-acogera-una-jornada-sobre-innovacion-con-la-resina/
19/10/2018	sorianoticias.com	Spain	Local	Spanish	Jornada este martes en Tardelcuende sobre la mecanización y organización en el sector resinero	Generalist media / general public	http://sorianoticias.com/noticia/2018-10-19-jornada-tardelcuende-sobre-mecanizacion-organizacion-sector-resinero-52653
17/05/2018	Boletín COIM N° 48	Spain	National	Spanish	El I Foro de Bioeconomía Forestal del Suroeste de Europa sirve de escaparate para mostrar el modelo de gestión que se desarrolla en Castilla y León	Sectoral / specialised public	https://www.ingenierosdemontes.org/boletines/20180516.html
15/05/2018	madera-sostenible.com	Spain	National	Spanish	La innovación y la transferencia de conocimiento, claves para impulsar el sector resinero	Sectoral / specialised public	https://madera-sostenible.com/breves/la-innovacion-y-la-transferencia-de-conocimiento-claves-para-impulsar-el-sector-resinero/
15/05/2018	Información Europea de Castilla y León	Spain	Regional	Spanish	El I Foro de Bioeconomía Forestal del Suroeste de Europa sirve de escaparate para mostrar el modelo de gestión que se desarrolla en Castilla y León	Sectoral / specialised public	Not available.
14/05/2018	Newsletter <i>Indforma</i>	Spain	National	Spanish	La innovación y la transferencia de conocimiento, claves para impulsar el sector resinero	Sectoral / specialised public	http://www.cesefor.com/noticias/la-innovacion-y-la-transferencia-de-conocimiento-claves-para-impulsar-el-sector-resinero
19/12/2020	MedForest	Interregional	International	English	Collaborative networks on resin as raw material for the bioeconomy	Sectoral / specialised public	https://medforest.net/2020/12/19/collaborative-networks-on-resin-as-raw-material-for-the-bioeconomy/
30/01/2020	Interreg Sudoe Website	Interregional	International	Spanish	SustForest Plus lanza un reto de innovación	Sectoral / specialised public	https://www.interreg-sudoe.eu/comunicacion/noticias-sudoe/334-los-proyectos-sudoe-en-enero
20/01/2020	EFIMED Network News	Interregional	International	English	Participatory process to improve professional resin tapping	Sectoral / specialised public	https://medforest.net/2020/01/20/participatory-process-to-improve-professional-resin-tapping/
29/03/2019	MedForest	Interregional	International	English	The INCREDIBLE consortium calls for a common label for European resin	Sectoral / specialised public	https://medforest.net/2019/03/29/the-incredible-consortium-calls-for-a-common-label-for-european-resin/
27/02/2019	SustForest Plus Project Website	Interregional	International	Spanish	SustForest Plus participa en el evento organizado por el proyecto INCREDIBLE la extracción de la resina como pieza clave de la	Sectoral / specialised public	https://www.sust-forest.eu/es/noticia/sustforest-plus-participa-en-el-evento-organizado-por-el-proyecto-incredibile-la-extraccion

					multifuncionalidad forestal sostenible	
19/12/2018	MedForest	Interregional	International	English	Interregional Workshop 'Resin resource modelling in a context of climate change'	Sectoral / specialised public https://medforest.net/2018/12/19/interregional-workshop-resin-resource-modelling-in-a-context-of-climate-change/

8. Wild Nuts and Berries

8.1. “Knowledge in practice” articles on Wild Nuts and Berries – An overview

The **iNet of Wild Nuts and Berries** focuses on sharing knowledge around pests, diseases and fruit pests are one of the main fronts to address, besides the adoption of new forms of forest management taking into account adaptation to climate change, with the focus on the fact that new business opportunities must guarantee traceability and product quality throughout the value chain (AD1).

INCREDIBLE partners produced 71 dissemination items specifically related to Wild Nuts and berries, mainly disseminated at Spanish, Portuguese, and Interregional level. These articles include 41 articles in sectorial and practitioners’ magazines and journals as well as 30 articles targeted at broader audiences, through regional, national newspapers and dissemination blogs. The complete list of articles is provided in Section 8.2.

8.2. Table of dissemination items

Table 6. Dissemination items of the Wild Nuts and Berries iNet

Date	MEDIA/JOURNAL	COUNTRY	LEVEL	LANGUAGE	TITLE	AUDIENCE TYPE	LINK
14/12/2020	UNAC website	Portugal	National	Portuguese	PINHA E PINHÃO: Desafios e Oportunidades	Sectoral / specialised public	http://unac.pt/index.php/eventos-noticias/noticias/item/261-webinar-junta-fileiras-do-pinhao-amendoa-e-castanha
14/12/2020	VIDA Rural	Portugal	National	Portuguese	Webinar: “Pinha e Pinhão – Desafios e Oportunidades”	Sectoral / specialised public	https://www.vidarural.pt/producao/webinar-pinha-e-pinhao-desafios-e-oportunidades/
14/12/2020	Redrural.gov	Portugal	National	Portuguese	Webinar “Pinha e Pinhão: Desafios e Oportunidades” 14 Dez 2020	Sectoral / specialised public	https://inovacao.rederural.gov.pt/9-destaque-inov/1099-webinar-pinha-e-pinhao-desafios-e-oportunidades-14-dez-2020
09/12/2020	Agricultura e Mar	Portugal	National	Portuguese	Desafios e oportunidades da pinha e pinhão. Exemplos da amêndoa e castanha. Webinar. Inscrições gratuitas	Sectoral / specialised public	https://agriculturaemar.com/desafios-e-oportunidades-da-pinha-e-pinhao-exemplos-da-amendoa-e-castanha-webinar-inscricoes-gratuitas/
14/12/2020	Florestas	Portugal	National	Portuguese	Webinar – Pinha e Pinhão: desafios e oportunidades	Sectoral / specialised public	https://florestas.pt/noticias-e-agenda/webinar-pinha-e-pinhao-desafios-e-oportunidades/
14/12/2020	Agrozapp	Portugal	National	Portuguese	Webinar – Pinha e Pinhão: desafios e oportunidades	Sectoral / specialised public	https://www.agrozapp.pt/eventos/Outros/webinar-pinha-e-pinho-desafios-e-oportunidades
14/12/2020	CAP.pt	Portugal	National	Portuguese	Webinar: Fileiras do pinhão, amêndoa e castanha unidas na valorização dos frutos secos	Sectoral / specialised public	https://www.cap.pt/noticias-cap/agricultura-e-floresta/webinar-fileiras-do-pinhao-amendoa-e-castanha-unidas-na-valorizacao-dos-frutos-secos
30/10/2019	Agroportal	Portugal	National	Portuguese	O Pinheiro Manso e o Pinhão – Mais conhecimento, Melhor gestão – 30 de outubro – Lisboa	Sectoral / specialised public	https://www.agroportal.pt/o-pinheiro-manso-e-o-pinhao-mais-conhecimento-melhor-gestao-30-de-outubro-lisboa/
30/10/2019	Voz Do Campo.pt	Portugal	National	Portuguese	Ciclo de Sessões CEF: Da Investigação à Aplicação	Sectoral / specialised public	https://vozdocampo.pt/2019/10/27/ciclo-de-sessoes-cef-da-investigacao-a-aplicacao/
2019	APAS Floresta	Portugal	National	Portuguese	InforFloresta	Sectoral / specialised public	https://www.apasfloresta.pt/files/inforfloresta/inforfloresta_36_site.pdf
11/12/2020	Newsletter Indforma	Spain	National	Spanish	Jornada para plantear los retos y oportunidades del sector del piñón, y qué	Sectoral / specialised public	https://bit.ly/3olMOoh

					aprender de otros frutos secos forestales		
12/11/2020	Newsletter Indforma	Spain	National	Spanish	Más de 20 charlas conforman el programa de las Jornadas Técnicas de Biocastanea 2020	Sectoral / specialised public	http://ceseфор.com/noticias/mas-de-20-charlas-conforman-el-programa-de-las-jornadas-tecnicas-de-biocastanea-2020
11/12/2019	Newsletter Indforma	Spain	National	Spanish	El sector de la castaña acude al Parlamento Europeo a presentar las demandas del sector	Sectoral / specialised public	https://bit.ly/39p0lqW
08/10/2019	campocyl.es	Spain	Regional	Spanish	El proyecto INCREDIBLE busca alternativas rentables para la adaptación al cambio climático de las producciones forestales	Sectoral / specialised public	https://www.campocyl.es/category/sector/el-proyecto-incredibile-busca-alternativas-rentables-para-la-adaptacion-al-cambio-climatico-de-las-producciones-forestales/
08/10/2019	Agencia ICAL	Spain	Regional	Spanish	La Uva aborda mañana en una jornada el impacto del cambio climático en la producción forestal con propietarios y expertos	Generalist media / general public	Not available.
08/10/2019	eldiadevalladolid.com	Spain	Local	Spanish	Cambio climático y producción forestal, a debate en la Uva	Generalist media / general public	https://www.eldiadevalladolid.com/noticia/ZB78BB8E5-CFB2-D6B5-CFB7742D48B4EAE3/Cambio-climatico-y-produccion-forestal-a-debate-en-la-UVa
07/10/2019	Web Universidad de Valladolid	Spain	National	Spanish	Jornada de transferencia Escenarios de Cambio climático y Producciones Forestales, ¿cómo se pueden adaptar las masas forestales? Claves para propietarios y gestores en la cuenca central del Duero	Sectoral / specialised public	http://eventos.uva.es/agenda/show_event/40651/jornada-de-transferencia-escenarios-de-cambio-climatico-y-producciones-forestales-como-se-pueden-ad.html
07/10/2019	agronewscastillayleon.com	Spain	Regional	Spanish	El proyecto INCREDIBLE busca alternativas rentables para la adaptación al cambio climático de las producciones forestales	Sectoral / specialised public	https://www.agronewscastillayleon.com/el-proyecto-incredibile-busca-alternativas-rentables-para-la-adaptacion-al-cambio-climatico-de-las
06/10/2019	madera-sostenible.com	Spain	National	Spanish	El proyecto INCREDIBLE busca alternativas rentables para la adaptación al cambio climático de las producciones forestales	Sectoral / specialised public	https://madera-sostenible.com/forestal/el-proyecto-incredibile-busca-alternativas-rentables-para-la-adaptacion-al-cambio-climatico-de-las-producciones-forestales/
05/10/2019	El Mundo-Diario de Soria	Spain	Local	Spanish	INCREDIBLE busca alternativas rentables en el sector forestal	Generalist media / general public	Not available.
05/10/2019	laagriculturadigital.com	Spain	National	Spanish	INCREDIBLE, alternativas rentables para la adaptación al cambio climático de las	Sectoral / specialised public	https://laagriculturadigital.com/incredibile-alternativas-rentables-para-la

					producciones forestales no maderables		
04/10/2019	Newsletter Indforma	Spain	National	Spanish	El proyecto INCREDIBLE busca alternativas rentables para la adaptación al cambio climático de las producciones forestales	Sectoral / specialised public	http://ceseфор.com/noticias/el-proyecto-incredible-busca-alternativas-rentables-para-la-adaptacion-al-cambio-climatico
04/10/2019	Agencia ICAL	Spain	Regional	Spanish	Valladolid acoge el 9 de octubre una jornada sobre cambio climático y producciones forestales	Generalist media / general public	Not available.
04/10/2019	desdesoria.es	Spain	Local	Spanish	El proyecto Incredible busca alternativas rentables para la adaptación al cambio climático de las producciones forestales	Generalist media / general public	http://www.desdesoria.es/2019/10/04/el-proyecto-incredible-busca-alternativas-rentables-para-la-adaptacion-al-cambio-climatico-de-las-producciones-forestales/
04/10/2019	sorianoticias.com	Spain	Local	Spanish	Valladolid acoge la jornada INCREDIBLE sobre alternativas a la adaptación del cambio climático	Generalist media / general public	http://sorianoticias.com/noticia/2019-10-04-valladolid-acoge-jornada-incredible-sobre-alternativas-adaptacion-cambio-climatico-61739
04/10/2019	eldiadevalladolid.com	Spain	Local	Spanish	Valladolid acoge el día 9 una jornada sobre cambio climático	Generalist media / general public	https://www.eldiadevalladolid.com/noticia/ZEA4B6C49-B905-38E1-8A02D397885716EB/Valladolid-acoge-el-dia-9-una-jornada-sobre-cambio-climatico
04/10/2019	observatoriodehesamontado.es	Spain	Regional	Spanish	El proyecto INCREDIBLE busca alternativas rentables para la adaptación al cambio climático de las producciones forestales	Sectoral / specialised public	http://observatoriodehesamontado.juntaex.es/index.php?modulo=noticias&pagina=view.php&id=1691
04/10/2019	interempresas.net	Spain	National	Spanish	INCREDIBLE, alternativas rentables para la adaptación al cambio climático de las producciones forestales no maderables	Sectoral / specialised public	https://www.interempresas.net/Grandes-cultivos/Articulos/264541-INCREDIBLE-alternativas-rentables-adaptacion-cambio-climatico-producciones-forestales-no.html
05/07/2019	Newsletter Indforma	Spain	National	Spanish	La respuesta coordinada, clave para hacer frente al cambio climático y a las plagas que afectan al piñón y a la castaña	Sectoral / specialised public	http://ceseфор.com/noticias/la-respuesta-coordinada-clave-para-hacer-frente-al-cambio-climatico-y-las-plagas-que
28/06/2019	madera-sostenible.com	Spain	National	Spanish	La respuesta coordinada es clave para frenar las plagas que afectan al piñón y a la castaña	Sectoral / specialised public	https://madera-sostenible.com/forestal/la-respuesta-coordinada-es-clave-para-frenar-a-las-plagas-que-afectan-al-pinon-y-a-la-castana/
25/06/2019	diariodeleon.es	Spain	Local	Spanish	Los expertos coinciden en señalar el fin del cultivo tradicional de castaña	Generalist media / general public	https://www.diariodeleon.es/articulo/bierzo/expertos-coinciden-senalar-fin-cultivo-tradicional-castana/201906250400001901531.html

24/06/2019	zamora24horas.com	Spain	Local	Spanish	La respuesta coordinada, clave para hacer frente al cambio climático y a las plagas que afectan al piñón y a la castaña	Generalist media / general public	https://www.zamora24horas.com/texto-diario/mostrar/1463105/respuesta-coordinada-clave-hacer-frente-cambio-climatico-plagas-afectan-pinon-castana
24/06/2019	INIA website	Spain	National	Spanish	La respuesta coordinada, clave para hacer frente al cambio climático y a las plagas que afectan al piñón y a la castaña	Sectoral / specialised public	http://wwwsp.inia.es/Comunicacion/Notasdeprensa/Lists/Notas%20Prensa/Attachments/278/NP%20Incredible%20Palencia%20Junio%202019.pdf
14/06/2019	zamora3punto0.com	Spain	Local	Spanish	Investigadores forestales turcos visitan los castaños de Aliste con técnicos de la Diputación	Generalist media / general public	https://zamora3punto0.com/investigadores-forestales-turcos-visit-an-los-castanos-de-aliste-con-tecnicos-de-la-diputacion/
14/06/2019	El Mundo. Heraldo-Diario de Soria	Spain	Local	Spanish	Cesefor enseña los trabajos sobre el castaño	Generalist media / general public	
14/06/2019	campocyl.es	Spain	Regional	Spanish	Palencia acoge un encuentro de Cesefor sobre castaño, plagas y cambio climático	Sectoral / specialised public	https://www.campocyl.es/category/sector/palencia-acoge-un-encuentro-de-cesefor-sobre-castano-plagas-y-cambio-climatico/
14/06/2019	noticiascyl.com	Spain	Regional	Spanish	Investigadores forestales turcos visitan los castaños de Aliste	Generalist media / general public	https://www.noticiascyl.com/zamora/provincia-zamora/2019/06/14/investigadores-forestales-turcos-visit-an-los-castanos-de-aliste/
14/06/2019	Prensa Diputación Zamora	Spain	Local	Spanish	Investigadores forestales turcos visitan los castaños de Aliste con técnicos de la Diputación de Zamora	Generalist media / general public	http://www.diputaciondezamora.es/index.asp?MP=8&MS=22&MN=2&TR=A&IDR=18&id=2204&r=1920*1080
14/06/2019	Agencia ICAL	Spain	Regional	Spanish	Investigadores forestales de Turquía visitan plantaciones de castaño en la provincia de Zamora	Generalist media / general public	Not available.
14/06/2019	zamora24horas.com	Spain	Local	Spanish	Investigadores forestales turcos visitan los castaños de Aliste con técnicos de la Diputación de Zamora	Generalist media / general public	https://www.zamora24horas.com/texto-diario/mostrar/1454125/investigadores-forestales-turcos-visit-an-castanos-aliste-tecnicos-diputacion-zamora
13/06/2019	elmirondesoria.es	Spain	Local	Spanish	Cesefor muestra a expertos del Mediterráneo sus trabajos sobre el castaño	Generalist media / general public	https://elmirondesoria.es/cyl/castilla-y-leon/cesefor-muestra-a-expertos-del-mediterraneo-sus-trabajos-sobre-el-castano
13/06/2019	sorianoticias.com	Spain	Local	Spanish	Cesefor muestra a expertos del Mediterráneo sus avances sobre castaño, plagas y cambio climático	Generalist media / general public	http://sorianoticias.com/noticia/2019-06-13-cesefor-muestra-expertos-mediterraneo-sus-avances-sobre-castano-plagas-cambio-climatico-59061
13/06/2019	desdesoria.es	Spain	Local	Spanish	Cesefor muestra a expertos del Mediterráneo sus trabajos sobre castaño, plagas y cambio climático	Generalist media / general public	http://www.desdesoria.es/2019/06/13/cesefor-muestra-a-expertos-del-mediterraneo-sus-trabajos-sobre-castano-plagas-y-cambio-climatico/

13/06/2019	Newsletter Indforma	Spain	National	Spanish	Expertos del Mediterráneo se reúnen para abordar la incidencia de las plagas y el cambio climático en el castaño	Sectoral / specialised public	http://ceseфор.com/noticias/expertos-del-mediterraneo-se-reunen-para-abordar-la-incidencia-de-las-plagas-y-el-cambio
03/06/2019	campocyl.es	Spain	Regional	Spanish	La UVa acoge una jornada sobre frutos secos en tiempos de nuevas plagas, enfermedades y cambio climático	Sectoral / specialised public	https://www.campocyl.es/category/otros-cultivos/la-uva-acoge-una-jornada-sobre-frutos-secos-en-tiempos-de-nuevas-plagas-enfermedades-y-cambio-climatico/
31/05/2019	madera-sostenible.com	Spain	National	Spanish	Jornada en la UVA sobre frutos y frutos secos en tiempos de nuevas plagas y cambio climático	Sectoral / specialised public	https://madera-sostenible.com/forestal/jornada-en-la-uva-sobre-frutos-y-frutos-secos-en-tiempos-de-nuevas-plagas-y-cambio-climatico/
31/05/2019	Newsletter Indforma	Spain	National	Spanish	Jornada del proyecto INCREDIBLE sobre 'Frutos y frutos secos en tiempos de nuevas plagas, enfermedades y cambio climático'	Sectoral / specialised public	http://ceseфор.com/noticias/jornada-del-proyecto-incredibile-sobre-frutos-y-frutos-secos-en-tiempos-de-nuevas-plagas
31/05/2019	Agencia ICAL	Spain	Regional	Spanish	Los frutos, el cambio climático y las nuevas enfermedades y plagas, protagonistas de un jornada en la Yutera (Palencia)	Generalist media / general public	Not available.
31/05/2019	zamoranews.com	Spain	Local	Spanish	Interesante jornada en la Universidad de Valladolid sobre 'Frutos y frutos secos en tiempos de nuevas plagas, enfermedades y cambio climático'	Generalist media / general public	https://zamoranews.com/castilla-y-leon/item/45052-interesante-jornada-en-la-universidad-de-valladolid-sobre-frutos-y-frutos-secos-en-tiempos-de-nuevas-plagas-enfermedades-y-cambio-climatico
22/05/2019	diariodeleon.es	Spain	Local	Spanish	Balboa acoge hoy una jornada sobre el papel del castaño en el desarrollo del medio rural	Generalist media / general public	https://www.diariodeleon.es/noticias/bierzo/balboa-acoge-hoy-jornada-papel-castano-desarrollo-medio-rural_1337225.html
17/05/2019	diariodeleon.es	Spain	Local	Spanish	Un grupo de expertos analizará en Balboa la importancia del castaño para el desarrollo rural	Generalist media / general public	https://www.diariodeleon.es/noticias/bierzo/grupo-expertos-analizara-balboa-importancia-castano-desarrollo-rural_1335962.html
16/05/2019	lanuevacronica.com	Spain	Local	Spanish	Balboa acoge una jornada sobre el potencial de castaño en el Bierzo	Generalist media / general public	https://www.lanuevacronica.com/balboa-acoge-una-jornada-sobre-el-potencial-de-castano-en-el-bierzo
16/05/2019	elbierzodigital.com	Spain	Local	Spanish	Una jornada analizará en Balboa las oportunidades que ofrece el aprovechamiento del castaño para el desarrollo rural	Generalist media / general public	https://www.elbierzodigital.com/una-jornada-analizara-en-balboa-las-oportunidades-que-ofrece-el-aprovechamiento-del-castano-para-el-desarrollo-rural/288043

16/05/2019	Agencia ICAL	Spain	Regional	Spanish	Una jornada analizará en Balboa (León) las oportunidades que ofrece el aprovechamiento del castaño para el desarrollo rural	Generalist media / general public	http://www.icalnews.com/Mostrar.cfm/noticias/l/jornada/analizara/balboa/leon/oportunidades/ofrece/aprovechamiento/castano/desarrollo/rural/457018
16/05/2019	ileon.com	Spain	Local	Spanish	Analizan en Balboa las oportunidades que ofrece el aprovechamiento del castaño para el desarrollo rural	Generalist media / general public	https://www.ileon.com/actualidad/097594/analizan-en-balboa-las-oportunidades-que-ofrece-el-aprovechamiento-del-castano-para-el-desarrollo-rural
16/05/2019	Newsletter <i>Indforma</i>	Spain	National	Spanish	El proyecto INCREDIBLE celebra en Balboa una jornada 'de la ciencia a la práctica' del castaño	Sectoral / specialised public	http://ceseфор.com/noticias/el-proyecto-incredibile-celebra-en-balboa-una-jornada-de-la-ciencia-la-practica-del-castano
16/05/2019	infobierzo.com	Spain	Local	Spanish	Jornada 'de la ciencia a la práctica' del aprovechamiento del castaño en la Casa de las Gentes de Balboa	Generalist media / general public	https://www.infobierzo.com/jornada-de-la-ciencia-a-la-practica-del-aprovechamiento-del-castano-en-la-casa-de-las-gentes-de-balboa/471555/
16/05/2019	agendadelbierzo.com	Spain	Local	Spanish	Jornada 'de la ciencia a la práctica' del aprovechamiento del castaño en la Casa de las Gentes de Balboa	Generalist media / general public	https://agendadelbierzo.com/otros-eventos/jornada-aprovechamiento-castano-balboa/?fbclid=IwAR0z8a-ThKJBSjW3oK6jAtZBXT0V0IRN6Wj2A5jmUwqiqiA08xEvdQEInat4
16/05/2019	elbierzonoticias.com	Spain	Local	Spanish	Una jornada analizará en Balboa las oportunidades que ofrece el aprovechamiento del castaño para el desarrollo rural	Generalist media / general public	https://www.elbierzonoticias.com/bierzo/jornada-analizara-balboa-20190516124437-nt.html
19/09/2018	europapress.es	Spain	National	Spanish	Valladolid acoge mañana la jornada 'Mejoras e innovación en la producción del piñón nacional'	Generalist media / general public	http://www.europapress.es/castilla-y-leon/noticia-valladolid-acoge-manana-jornada-mejoras-innovacion-produccion-pinon-nacional-20180919113711.html
17/09/2018	agronewscastillayleon.com	Spain	Regional	Spanish	El próximo 20 de septiembre Valladolid acogerá la jornada "Mejoras e innovación en la producción del piñón nacional"	Sectoral / specialised public	http://www.agronewscastillayleon.com/el-proximo-20-de-septiembre-valladolid-acogera-la-jornada-mejoras-e-innovacion-en-la-produccion-de/
11/06/2018	Newsletter <i>Indforma</i>	Spain	National	Spanish	El proyecto INCREDIBLE lanza esta semana en Portugal una nueva red de innovación en productos forestales no maderables	Sectoral / specialised public	http://www.ceseфор.com/noticias/el-proyecto-incredibile-lanza-esta-semana-en-portugal-una-nueva-red-de-innovacion-en
21/12/2020	MedForest	Interregional	International	English	Cone and pine nuts: challenges and opportunities	Sectoral / specialised public	https://medforest.net/2020/12/21/cone-and-pine-nuts-challenges-and-opportunities/
24/06/2019	MedForest	Interregional	International	English	Pests, diseases and climate change impact on chestnut and pine nut supply	Sectoral / specialised public	https://medforest.net/2019/06/24/pests-diseases-and-climate-change-impact-on-chestnut-and-pine-nut-supply/

02/05/2019	MedForest	Interregional	International	English	Chestnut orchards: an opportunity for rural development	Sectoral / specialised public	https://medforest.net/2019/05/02/chestnut-orchards-an-opportunity-for-rural-development/
16/04/2019	MedForest	Interregional	International	English	Wild harvest in time of new pests, diseases and climate change	Sectoral / specialised public	https://medforest.net/2019/04/16/wild-harvest-in-time-of-new-pests-diseases-and-climate-change/
27/03/2019	MedForest	Interregional	International	English	Release of elite stone pine clones for orchard plantations	Sectoral / specialised public	https://medforest.net/2019/03/27/%ef%bb%bfrelease-of-elite-stone-pine-clones-for-orchard-plantations/
29/09/2018	EFIMED News	Interregional	International	English	Spanish pine nut sector searches for solutions to the serious situation caused by invasive pest	Sectoral / specialised public	<u>Not available.</u>
26/09/2018	EFIMED News	Interregional	International	English	Knowledge exchange between pine nut experts	Sectoral / specialised public	<u>Not available.</u>
28/06/2018	EFIMED Network News	Interregional	International	English	Value chain actors and stakeholders join international network on wild nuts & berries to identify priority themes	Sectoral / specialised public	<u>Not available.</u>
01/2020	Book published by INIA	Spain	National	Spanish	Chapter 5. El piñón mediterráneo in book Los productos forestales no madereros en España: del monte a la industria, Monografías	Sectoral / specialised public	https://www.researchgate.net/publication/341940884_Capitulo_5_El_pinon_mediterraneo

9. Inter-iNets dissemination articles

Beside iNet-specific dissemination articles, INCREDIBLE partners produced a series of dissemination items aiming at disseminating multiple aspects of NWFPs altogether. These include: project showcasing articles (e.g. promotion of the project activities, and main achievements), and lessons learned from the iterative multi-actor process undertaken with INCREDIBLE stakeholders across the project life-cycle. The list provided in Table 9.1 includes 67 entries. Amongst these, 6 are scientific presentations at conferences, publications, and book chapters.

9.1. Table of dissemination items

Table 7. Inter-iNets dissemination items.

Date	MEDIA/JOURNAL	COUNTRY	LEVEL	LANGUAGE	TITLE	AUDIENCE TYPE	LINK
19/7/2018	pbnews	Greece	Local	Greek	Μια «Απίθανη» συνεργασία για τα μη ξυλώδη δασικά προϊόντα στη Μεσόγειο	Generalist media / general public	https://pbnews.gr/%CE%BC%CE%B9%CE%B1-%CE%B1%CF%80%CE%AF%CE%B8%CE%B1%CE%BD%CE%B7-%CF%83%CF%85%CE%BD%CE%B5%CF%81%CE%B3%CE%B1%CF%83%CE%AF%CE%B1-%CE%B3%CE%B9%CE%B1-%CF%84%CE%B1-%CE%BC%CE%B7-%CE%BE%CF%85%CE%BB%CF%8E/
09/05/2019	University of Ioannina website	Greece	National	English	Γενικά Νέα (General news): INCREDIBLE Events Bulletin 2	Sectoral / specialised public	http://www.rc.uoi.gr/index.php/nea-anakoinoseis/genika-nea/3029-incredible-project-upcoming-events-newsletter
12/12/2017	ΤΥΠΟΣi	Greece	Local	Greek	Τι κοινό έχουν ο φελλός, το ρετσίνι και τα αρωματικά φυτά;	Generalist media / general public	https://typos-i.gr/article/ti-koino-exoyn-o-fellos-retsini-kai-ta-aromatika-fyta
10/12/2017	thesseconomy.gr	Greece	Regional	Greek	INCREDible: Δίκτυα καινοτομίας για μανιτάρια-τρούφες και αρωματικά-φαρμακευτικά φυτά – Συμμετέχει το Πανεπιστήμιο Ιωαννίνων	Generalist media / general public	Not available.
09/12/2017	olympia.gr	Greece	National	Greek	Πρόγραμμα INCREDible: Δίκτυα καινοτομίας για τα προϊόντα του δάσους (in Greek)	Generalist media / general public	https://olympia.gr/2017/12/09/%CF%80%CF%81%CF%8C%CE%B3%CF%81%CE%B1%CE%BC%CE%BC%CE%B1-incredible-%CE%B4%CE%AF%CE%BA%CF%84%CF%85%CE%B1-%CE%BA%CE%B1%CE%B9%CE%BD%CE%BF%CF%84%CE%BF%CE%BC%CE%AF%CE%B1%CF%82-%CE%B3%CE%B9%CE%B1-%CF%84/
08/12/2017	dasarxeio.com	Greece	National	Greek	Πρόγραμμα INCREDible: Δίκτυα καινοτομίας για τα προϊόντα του δάσους (in Greek)	Sectoral / specialised public	https://dasarxeio.com/2017/12/08/51740/
08/12/2017	University of Ioannina website	Greece	National	Greek	Πρόγραμμα INCREDible: Δίκτυα καινοτομίας για τα προϊόντα του δάσους (in Greek)	Sectoral / specialised public	http://www.uoi.gr/programma-incredible-diktya-kenotomias-gia-ta-proionta-tou-dasous/
2019	ReteRurale.it	Italy	National	Italian	Rapporto sullo stato delle foreste e del settore forestale in Italia - RAF	Sectoral / specialised public	https://www.reterurale.it/flex/cm/pages/ServeBLOB.php/L/IT/IDPagina/19231
15/06/2019	sardegnaforeste.it	Italy	Regional	Italian	Open Innovation Challenge: selezione di 5 idee innovative	Sectoral / specialised public	http://www.sardegnaforeste.it/notizia/open-innovation-challenge-selezione-di-5-idee-innovative
04/06/2019	vidarural.pt	Portugal	National	Portuguese	Projecto Incredible premeia ideias inovadoras que aumentem valor dos produtos florestais	Sectoral / specialised public	https://www.vidarural.pt/agroindustria/projecto-incredible-premeia-ideias-inovadoras-que-aumentem-valor-dos-produtos-florestais/

25/09/2020	Newsletter Indforma	Spain	National	Spanish	El proyecto INCREDIBLE desarrolla su tercer seminario transversal en colaboración con SustForest Plus	Sectoral / specialised public	http://ceseфор.com/noticias/el-proyecto-incredible-desarrolla-su-tercer-seminario-transversal-en-colaboracion-con
23/09/2020	desdesoria.es	Spain	National	Spanish	Ceseфор organiza idiForest, innovación y tecnologías para productos forestales no maderables	Generalist media / general public	https://www.desdesoria.es/2020/09/23/ceseфор-organiza-idiforest-innovacion-y-tecnologias-para-productos-forestales-no-maderables/
18/09/2020	Newsletter Indforma	Spain	National	Spanish	idiForest se celebrará de forma telemática del 6 al 9 de octubre	Sectoral / specialised public	http://ceseфор.com/noticias/idiforest-se-celebrara-de-forma-telematica-del-6-al-9-de-octubre
17/06/2020	Newsletter Indforma	Spain	National	Spanish	idiForest, aplazado temporalmente por la COVID-19, se celebrará en septiembre	Sectoral / specialised public	http://ceseфор.com/noticias/idiforest-aplazado-temporalmente-por-la-covid-19-se-celebrara-en-septiembre
19/05/2020	Web CIF de Lourizán	Spain	Regional	Spanish	Colaboración del CIF de Lourizán en el proyecto INCREDIBLE	Sectoral / specialised public	https://lourizan.xunta.gal/es/noticias/colaboracion-del-cif-de-lourizan-en-el-proyecto-incredible
06/04/2020	segoviaudaz.es	Spain	Regional	Spanish	"Driada", un proyecto segoviano premiado por Sustforest Plus	Generalist media / general public	https://segoviaudaz.es/driada-un-proyecto-segoviano-premiado-por-sustforest-plus/
02/03/2020	campocyl.es	Spain	Regional	Spanish	Más allá de la madera: la actividad cinegética como fuente de riqueza del bosque	Sectoral / specialised public	https://www.campocyl.es/category/sector/mas-alla-de-la-madera-la-actividad-cinegetica-como-fuente-de-riqueza-del-bosque/
28/02/2020	Agencia ICAL	Spain	Regional	Spanish	Ceseфор presenta en un seminario internacional sus desarrollos de digitalización y minería de datos con subastasdecaza.com	Generalist media / general public	Not available.
28/02/2020	desdesoria.es	Spain	Local	Spanish	Ceseфор habla en Barcelona sobre innovación en productos forestales no maderables	Generalist media / general public	https://www.desdesoria.es/2020/02/28/ceseфор-habla-en-barcelona-sobre-innovacion-en-productos-forestales-no-maderables/
28/02/2020	sorianoticias.com	Spain	Local	Spanish	Ceseфор defiende en Barcelona actividad cinegética como fuente de riqueza de los bosques	Generalist media / general public	http://sorianoticias.com/amp/noticia/2020-02-28-ceseфор-defiende-actividad-cinegetica-como-fuente-riqueza-bosques-65666
28/02/2020	elmirondesoria.es	Spain	Local	Spanish	Ceseфор presenta sus desarrollos en digitalización y minería	Generalist media / general public	https://elmirondesoria.es/soria/capital/ceseфор-present-sus-desarrollos-en-digitalizacion-y-mineria
28/02/2020	zamoranews.com	Spain	Local	Spanish	Más allá de la madera: La actividad cinegética como fuente de riqueza de nuestros bosques	Generalist media / general public	https://zamoranews.com/magazinezamora/reportajes-zamora/item/53167-mas-alla-de-la-madera-la-actividad-cinegetica-como-fuente-de-riqueza-de-nuestros-bosques
28/02/2020	soriativ.com	Spain	Local	Spanish	Más allá de la madera: La actividad cinegética como fuente de riqueza de nuestros bosques	Generalist media / general public	http://soriativ.com/mas-alla-de-la-madera-la-actividad-cinegetica-como-fuente-de-riqueza-de-nuestros-bosques/

28/02/2020	Newsletter <i>Indforma</i>	Spain	National	Spanish	Más allá de la madera: La actividad cinegética como fuente de riqueza de nuestros bosques	Sectoral / specialised public	http://ceseфор.com/noticias/mas-alla-de-la-madera-la-actividad-cinegetica-como-fuente-de-riqueza-de-nuestros-bosques
22/01/2021	MedForest	Interregional	International	English	“Powerful Seeds” wins 1st place conservation tech prize for reforestation project	Sectoral / specialised public	https://medforest.net/2021/01/22/powerful-seeds-by-dronecoria-wins-1st-place-conservation-tech-prize-for-reforestation-project/
29/11/2020	MedForest	Interregional	International	English	Knowledge exchange on agroforestry and climate change innovations	Sectoral / specialised public	https://medforest.net/2020/11/29/agroforestry-and-climate-change-innovations-knowledge-exchange-beyond-projects/
06/11/2020	MedForest	Interregional	International	English	Webinar: Sustainable management of wild collected products	Sectoral / specialised public	https://medforest.net/2020/11/06/fao-webinar-sustainable-management-of-wild-collected-products/
28/10/2020	MedForest	Interregional	International	English	ICT and emerging technologies for competitiveness, sustainability and social impact of NWFP	Sectoral / specialised public	https://medforest.net/2020/10/28/ict-and-emerging-technologies-for-competitiveness-sustainability-and-social-impact-of-non-wood-forest-products/
09/10/2020	MedForest	Interregional	International	English	Global experts collaborate towards policy actions for NWFPs	Sectoral / specialised public	https://medforest.net/2020/10/09/global-experts-collaborate-towards-policy-actions-for-nwfps/
06/10/2020	MedForest	Interregional	International	English	EURAKNOS online event: Agroforestry and climate change innovations	Sectoral / specialised public	https://medforest.net/2020/10/06/euraknos-online-event-agroforestry-and-climate-change-innovations/
06-7/10/2020	IUFRO Conference (The social and ecological value added of small-scale forestry to the Bio-Economy)	Interregional	International	English	From an informal to a legal wild forest products economy: the Italian experience on new fiscal regulations	Sectoral / specialised public	https://www.iufro2020.eurac.edu/
26/06/2020	MedForest	Interregional	International	English	Aleppo Pine in Tunisia: Ecology, Management and Uses	Sectoral / specialised public	https://medforest.net/2020/06/26/aleppo-pine-in-tunisia-ecology-management-and-uses/
16/06/2020	EFIMED Newsletter	Interregional	International	English	idiForest: innovation and emerging technologies for NWFP	Sectoral / specialised public	https://medforest.net/2020/06/16/idiforest-innovation-and-emerging-technologies-for-nwfp/
02/03/2020	MedForest	Interregional	International	English	Businesses gather in Barcelona to discuss boost for rural economy	Sectoral / specialised public	https://medforest.net/2020/03/02/businesses-gather-in-barcelona-to-discuss-boost-for-rural-economy/
18/02/2020	MedForest	Interregional	International	English	Innovative businesses and entrepreneurship for NWFP	Sectoral / specialised public	https://medforest.net/2020/02/18/innovative-businesses-and-entrepreneurship-for-non-wood-forest-products/
13/01/2020	FAO Newsletter Non-wood Forest Products Update - Issue #18	Interregional	International	English	The Knowledge repository for Non-Wood Forest Products is now online!	Sectoral / specialised public	http://newsletters.fao.org/q/16vq2OeJ9zN/wv

19/12/2019	MedForest	Interregional	International	English	INCREDIBLE Knowledge Repository for NWFP now online!	Sectoral / specialised public	https://medforest.net/2019/12/19/incredible-knowledge-repository-for-nwfp-now-online/
12/12/2019	MedForest	Interregional	International	English	Innovation and entrepreneurship in NWFP marketplace	Sectoral / specialised public	https://medforest.net/2019/12/12/innovative-businesses-and-entrepreneurship-in-nwfp-cross-cutting-seminars-marketplace/
28/10/2019	MedForest	Interregional	International	English	Strategic time for INCREDIBLE NWFP	Sectoral / specialised public	https://medforest.net/2019/10/28/strategic-time-for-incredible-nwfp/
30/07/2019	MedForest	Interregional	International	English	Innovations for non-wood forest products: final call for applications!	Sectoral / specialised public	https://medforest.net/2019/07/30/innovations-for-non-wood-forest-products-final-call-for-applications/
12/06/2019	Silva Mediterranea Newsletter #32	Interregional	International	English	Forest-based Solutions: Linking NWFP with the Economy, Participatory Approaches	Sectoral / specialised public	http://www.fao.org/forestry/silva-mediterranea/95871/en/
12/06/2019	MedForest	Interregional	International	English	INCREDIBLE project present at the workshop on thematic networks in EU agricultural innovation	Sectoral / specialised public	https://medforest.net/2019/06/12/incredible-project-present-at-the-workshop-on-thematic-networks-in-eu-agricultural-innovation/
24/05/2019	EFI Network News 5-2019	Interregional	International	English	Territorial marketing via NWFP facilitates multifunctional forest management	Sectoral / specialised public	https://efi.int/articles/territorial-marketing-nwfp-facilitates-multifunctional-forest-management?utm_campaign=campaign_code&utm_content=category&utm_medium=email&utm_source=efi_newsletter
08/05/2019	NWFP Update May 2019 / Issue #16 (FAO NWFP bulletin)	Interregional	International	English	Open Innovation Challenge: prizes on offer for solutions to support Mediterranean NWFPs	Sectoral / specialised public	http://newsletters.fao.org/q/16vpgRuwwark/wv
29/04/2019	MedForest	Interregional	International	English	Mediterranean Forest Week highlights forests' key role for a sustainable future	Sectoral / specialised public	https://medforest.net/2019/04/29/vi-mediterranean-forest-week-highlights-forests-key-role-for-a-sustainable-future/
29/04/2019	MedForest	Interregional	International	English	New territory for non-wood forest products through INCREDIBLE cross-cutting initiative	Sectoral / specialised public	https://medforest.net/2019/04/29/new-territory-for-non-wood-forest-products-through-incredible-cross-cutting-initiative/
22/04/2019	MedForest	Interregional	International	English	Innovation networks on Mediterranean non-wood forest products	Sectoral / specialised public	https://medforest.net/2019/04/22/innovation-networks-on-mediterranean-non-wood-forest-products/
09/04/2019	MedForest	Interregional	International	English	Prizes on offer for solutions to support Mediterranean NWFP	Sectoral / specialised public	https://medforest.net/2019/04/09/open-innovation-challenge-prizes-on-offer-for-solutions-to-support-mediterranean-nwfp/
02/04/2019	MedForest	Interregional	International	English	Integrating NWFP in territorial marketing and ecosystem service value chains	Sectoral / specialised public	https://medforest.net/2019/04/02/integrating-nwfp-in-territorial-marketing-and-ecosystem-service-value-chains/

25/03/2019	MedForest	Interregional	International	English	Mediterranean Forest Week: join us in seeking forest-based solutions	Sectoral / specialised public	https://medforest.net/2019/03/25/mediterranean-forest-week-join-us-in-seeking-forest-based-solutions/
12/03/2019	MedForest	Interregional	International	English	Mediterranean Forest Week: Can forest-based solutions mitigate climate change?	Sectoral / specialised public	https://medforest.net/2019/03/12/mediterranean-forest-week-can-forest-based-solutions-mitigate-climate-change/
28/02/2019	MedForest	Interregional	International	English	Mediterranean Forest Week: Forest-based Solutions	Sectoral / specialised public	https://medforest.net/2019/02/28/mediterranean-forest-week-forest-based-solutions/
30/10/2018	MedForest	Interregional	International	English	Sharing knowledge from lab to field, from science to practice	Sectoral / specialised public	https://medforest.net/2018/10/30/sharing-knowledge-from-lab-to-field-from-science-to-practice/
19/09/2018	Silva Mediterranea FAO	Interregional	International	English	INCREDIBLE project launches new networks on non-wood forest products for the Mediterranean to boost innovation and knowledge transfer	Sectoral / specialised public	http://www.fao.org/forestry/silva-mediterranea/94903/en/
27/07/2018	EFIMED Network News	Interregional	International	English	New international networks on non-wood forest products for the Mediterranean	Sectoral / specialised public	Not available.
31/05/2018	EFIMED Network News	Interregional	International	English	Launch of Innovation Networks to boost innovation and knowledge transfer on NWFP	Sectoral / specialised public	Not available.
01/05/2018	NWFP Update! FAO NWFP newsletter	Interregional	International	English	Q&A with EU's INCREDIBLE Project	Sectoral / specialised public	http://www.fao.org/forestry/nwfp/94362/en/
04/12/2017	Forest Information Billboard 4/2017	Interregional	International	English	More than wood: Innovation and entrepreneurship in cork, resin, edibles and other forest products	Sectoral / specialised public	Not available.
04/12/2017	Forest Information Billboard 4/2017	Interregional	International	English	The start of an INCREDible new project	Sectoral / specialised public	Not available.
30/11/2017	EFIMED Network News	Interregional	International	English	More than wood: Innovation and entrepreneurship in cork, resin, edibles and other forest products	Sectoral / specialised public	Not available.
30/11/2017	EFIMED Network News	Interregional	International	English	INCREDible project kicks off in Barcelona	Sectoral / specialised public	Not available.
10/11/2017	EFIMED Network News	Interregional	International	English	The start of an INCREDible new project	Sectoral / specialised public	Not available.

01/2020	Book published by INIA	Spain	National	Spanish	Capitulo 13. Innovación en PFNMs: casos de éxito in book Los productos forestales no madereros en España: del monte a la industria, Monografías	Sectoral / specialised public	https://www.researchgate.net/publication/341940600_Capitulo_13_Innovacion_en_PFNMs_casos_de_exito
06/2019	Journal of Innovative Science and Engineering	Interregional	International	English	Innovation networks on Mediterranean Non Wood Forest Products	Sectoral / specialised public	https://www.researchgate.net/publication/341076447_Innovation_networks_on_Mediterranean_Non_Wood_Forest_Products
03/2020	Current Forestry Reports	Interregional	International	English	Sustainable Forest Management Beyond the Timber-Oriented Status Quo: Transitioning to Co-production of Timber and Non-wood Forest Products—a Global Perspective	Sectoral / specialised public	https://www.researchgate.net/publication/338557022_Sustainable_Forest_Management_Beyond_the_Timber-Oriented_Status_Quo_Transitioning_to_Co-production_of_Timber_and_Non-wood_Forest_Products-a_Global_Perspective
03/2019	ForestLIFE	Greece	National	Greek	Τα μη ξυλώδη δασικά προϊόντα ως μέσο στήριξης της οικονομίας του ορεινού χώρου, διαχείρισης και ανάδειξης των δασικών οικοσυστημάτων/ Non-Timber Forest Products as means of supporting mountainous economies and forest ecosystem management and promotion	Sectoral / specialised public	https://forestlife.gr/wp-content/uploads/2019/04/12StaraK_forest-life-21.3.2019.pdf
05/2018	Revista Foresta (@RevForesta)	Spain	National	Spanish	Productos forestales: más allá de la madera	Sectoral / specialised public	https://www.forestales.net/Canales/Ficha.aspx?IdMenu=b6947309-987f-4bff-808d-4e7e974ccaf8&Cod=261345d5-f243-48a3-9294-f4b5be2cca9d&Idioma=es-ES

